

The Role of Shadow Teacher in Inclusive School: A Literature Review

Fina Septi Aristya¹, Sowiyah², Riswanti Rini³

¹ Student of Education Administration, Universitas Lampung, Bandar Lampung, Indonesia

^{2,3} Lecturer of Education Administration, Universitas Lampung, Bandar Lampung, Indonesia

ABSTRACT: The importance of the role of special assistant teachers in inclusive schools is interesting to learn, especially in assisting children with special needs this article aims to examine the role of shadow teachers in inclusive schools. The article used in this literature review is an article obtained through Google Scholar by entering the keywords shadow teacher and inclusion school. Based on the results of a literature review of national and international articles that have been conducted, researchers found that there are several roles of special assistant teachers, including planning individual planning programs (PPI), designing assessments and mentoring strategies, modifying teaching materials, and coordinating with other teachers and parents.

KEYWORDS: Inclusive schools, Literature review, Shadow teachers

I. INTRODUCTION

Education has an important role and a fundamental right for every child [1]. The implementation of education can not be separated from a teacher as a determinant of the quality of Education. The quality of education in schools is determined by the performance of teachers in the learning process [2]. The role is reflected in how teachers carry out their duties and responsibilities [3], especially special assistant teachers who handle children with special needs. Children with special needs are defined as children who need special education and services to develop their potential perfectly [4]. Some of the conditions of children with special needs that are quite well known are disabilities or physical disabilities due to accidents or congenital, there are also children with special needs due to neurological developmental disorders such as Autistic Spectrum Disorder or Attention Deficit and Hyperactivity Disorder [5].

The provision of services to children with special needs can generally be accessed through formal education services for all children who are so diverse without exception in an inclusive institution [6]. Inclusion schools are schools where students who have the potential for intelligence and / or special talents get inclusive education together with students in general [7]. Inclusive education gives children with special needs the same opportunities as other students to learn in the same environment, fosters a culture of mutual respect for Individual Differences and ensures that each child receives the resources they need [8]. In inclusive schools, there are special assistant teachers who deal with children with special needs. Accompanying teachers are very useful and can improve the overall quality of children's learning in the classroom and improve efforts to handle children with special needs. Accompanying teachers are expected to help children in many ways, such as: concentration, communication, class participation, public relations, politeness and behavior management [9].

Therefore, based on The Director's Manual For Construction PSLB (2007) revealed that shadow teachers competence is specifically oriented to three main abilities, namely: (1) General ability, (2) Basic Ability, and (3) Special Ability. Teachers provide services and understand the special characteristics of children with special needs in accordance with their potential so that children with special needs can develop and explore their potential together with normal learners [10]. In field practice, shadow teachers usually accompany students with special needs in regular classrooms during the learning process [11]. Based on this description, it is necessary to know more about the role of special accompanying teachers in inclusive schools. Therefore, the researchers conducted a research review of national and international articles.

II. LITERATURE REVIEW

A. Shadow Teachers

Special Assistant Teachers are one of the buffers in the implementation of inclusive schools, because without shadow teachers, special programs (Individual learning programs/ PPI) cannot be fulfilled [12]. Furthermore, Yuwono defines it as teachers who have

knowledge and skills in the field of children with special needs, who assist or cooperate with regular school educators to realize inclusive teaching [13]. Teachers provide services for children with special needs in inclusion classes in order to develop all the abilities of each child. Shadow teachers are required to create their own strategies, methods and approaches in accordance with the needs of the child [14]. According to Rosita, the competence of shadow teachers is not only based on the four main teacher competencies (pedagogical, personality, professional, and social), but also specifically oriented to specific abilities [15].

B. Inclusive School

Inclusive education in Permendiknas No. 70 of 2009 is defined as a system of education that provides opportunities to all learners berkelainan and have the potential intelligence and/or special talent to follow the education or learning in an educational environment together with learners in general. Staub & Peck suggest that inclusive education is the placement of children with different levels of light, medium, and heavy in full in the regular classroom [16]. It is well recognized that inclusive education gives children with special needs the same opportunities as other students to learn in the same environment, fosters a culture of mutual respect for Individual Differences and ensures that each child receives the resources they need [17].

The main principle of inclusive education is that all children should learn together and aims to eliminate "all barriers to school enrollment and achievement" [18], emphasizing the importance of recognizing and respecting differences in abilities, culture, gender, language, social status and ethnic origin [19]. Therefore, the goal of inclusive education is to guarantee that all children have access to cheap, effective, relevant and appropriate education in their local communities and that all stakeholders foster an atmosphere conducive to learning [20].

III. METHOD

The method used in this study is a literature review. The source of data used in this study is the article. Source data obtained from national and international article searches on Google Scholar. The process of analyzing the article begins with the use of keywords: shadow teacher "or" school of inclusion. After reviewing the literature, there were 263,000 articles related to this theme and selected 10 articles taken according to the criteria. Next, the article is analyzed and compiled as a whole in the discussion written in this article.

Article criteria in this study are as follows:

- a. Shadow teachers and inclusive schools
- b. Research conducted at school
- c. Quantitative and qualitative articles
- d. Articles for the last 5 years, 2019-2023
- e. National and international articles

The chart below shows the skema method :

Figure 1. Skema Method

IV. RESULT AND DISCUSSION

The following is a review of the work that the author has done. The analysis was conducted as a large article on special teachers and inclusion schools. Literature review that has been done by the author is as follows:

Table 1. The Role of Shadow Teachers in Inclusive Schools

No	Title	Author & Year	Country	Method	Sample	Results
1.	The Role Of Special Guidance Teachers In Dealing With Learning Difficulties For Slow Learners At Sdn Cimone 7	Nurfadillah, S., Afifah, A., Putri, S.A., & Halimah, S. (2022)	Indonesia	Qualitative	Shadow teacher and disability childrens	The role of shadow teacher in the learning achievement of children with special needs include: as an advocate, as a source, as a teacher such as guiding their children while studying at home, always provide motivation to study hard. In addition, carry out special programs that are carried out daily, identify, modify teaching materials, conduct evaluations.
2.	The Role Of Parents And Shadow Teachers To Children With Special Needs (Slow Learner) In Sd Negeri 5 Arcawinangun	Khiyarusole h, U. (2019)	Indonesia	Qualitative	Parents and shadow teachers	The role of shadow teachers is to design and implement specificity programs. Identify, assess and develop Individual learning programs.
3.	The Role Of Special Guidance Teachers For Non-Special Education Graduates On The Service Of Children With Special Needs In Inclusive Schools In Lumajang Regency	Wardah, E. Y. (2019)	Indonesia	Qualitative	Shadow Teachers	Services for children with special needs can not run effectively due to the lack of knowledge of non-special education guidance teachers about children with special needs.
4.	Shadow Teacher Of Inclusive School In Palangka Raya	Faz, G.O & Hafid, I. (2023)	Indonesia	Qualitative	Shadow Teachers	The task of shadow teachers is to accompany children with special needs in the classroom to ensure that they remain adaptive and Classroom Conditions are conducive, encourage interaction with peers and educate the condition of children with special needs with their friends, actively communicate to schools and parents about the needs of children with special needs, and help children with special needs in
5.	The role of Classroom Teachers and Shadow Teachers in improving inclusive	Barlian, U.C., Wulandari, R.P., Said,	Indonesia	Qualitative	Coordinato r (ISSC).	Create a learning program for children with special needs in the form of PPI in accordance with their abilities.

	education services in Ibn Sina kindergarten	M., & Brilianti, N.L (2023)				
6.	Role Of Shadow Teacher In The Provision Of Academic And Social Support For Children With Special Needs At Inclusive Schools	Hamid, A, Ullah, H. M.I., & Faiz, Z. (2020)	Pakistan	Quantitative	Shadow Teachers	The role of a shadow teacher is to help the children needing to support activities by helping fill in the gaps in the learning procedure and overall assist the child to create academic and social abilities.
7.	The Role Of Shadow Teacher In Learning Management Of Children With Special Needs In Paud Terpadu Inklusi Bina Insan Kreatif Tasikmalaya	Hijriyani, Y.S, Andriani, F & Rosidin (2021)	Indonesia	Qualitative	Shadow Teacher	Shadow teacher applies various strategies to assist the development of disability students, in the academic, non-academic and self-developed fields.
8.	The Role Of Shadow Teacher In Improving Autistic Students Ability In Learning	Sabatin, I.M.A (2020)	Palestina	Quantitative	Shadow Teaher	Shadow teacher plays an important role in providing additional support, throughout the school day, academically and psychologically, to those students enrolled in the optimal learning (ol) program that need this additional support. In
9.	The role of Shadow Teachers in supporting Inclusion Programs at TKIT Lentera Insan CDEC Depok	Yunitasari, S.E., Emelda, Nofrianto, R., Heryani, Y, Eliyanah, Hafid. P.Y (2023)	Indonesia	Qualitative	Head of division HRD & Shdow Teachers	The involvement of shadow teachers in carrying out student identification, implementing individual learning programs, communicating with parents, carrying out training and intervention during children's activities at school, implementing learning evaluations, coordinating with class teachers, coordinating with student development teams in carrying out student development.
10.	The effectiveness of the role of shadow teachers in improving the quality of learning in Early Childhood	Aurina, A.N & Zulkarnaen, (2022)	Indonesia	Qualitative	Shadow Teachers	Shadow teachers in improving the quality of learning is very effective, we can observe from the perspective of learning, learning, to learning evaluation where teachers are in terms of achieving class, improving the quality of learning, and improving learning outcomes are already in the good category

This article discusses the role of shadow teachers in inclusive schools. Most of the articles discuss how big the role of special assistant teachers and some review the role of parents and class teachers in inclusive schools. Based on the article reviewed, there are various ways of collecting data related to the role of special assistant teachers in inclusive schools; the most commonly used are questionnaires, interviews and observation and documentation.

Table 1 shows that this study was conducted at various levels of Education from kindergarten, elementary, junior high and high school levels. Based on the results of the literature review, the results showed that there are several roles of shadow teachers against learning difficulties for children with special needs in schools [21], including designing and implementing individual learning programs and carrying out evaluations. This study reveals that the role of special guidance teachers in the learning achievement of children with special needs include: as an advocate, as a source, as a teacher who is able to guide and motivate. According to the findings of the study, special assistant teachers have implemented special programs that are carried out every day, identify, modify teaching materials, evaluate.

Different from Khiyarusoleh [22], who revealed that the role of shadow teachers in inclusive schools needs to be optimized in order to provide maximum learning services for children with special needs. According to the findings of the study, there are three important things that must be considered in the implementation of inclusive schools involving shadow teachers, including (1) the need for Standardization regarding recruitment, basic function duties, to shadow teachers ' wages, (2) it is important to be able to improve the competence of shadow teachers, teachers, to parents, and (3) communication between shadow teachers, class teachers, and parents must be established routinely and effectively.

This is in line with research conducted by Barlian [23], involving the role of the classroom teacher in improving inclusive education services. The findings revealed that the involvement of classroom teachers in inclusive education services is as a communication link between teachers and parents. Thus, with the cooperation between the classroom teacher and a special assistant teacher, can create the right learning process runs effectively and efficiently.

Furthermore, the results of research conducted by Hamid, Ullah & Faiz [24] the role of shadow teacher can build confidence in children and help in reading, writing, speaking, listening, peer relationships, eye contact, time management, greetings, completing work on time, playing with other children and developing the concept of right and wrong. The findings reveal that there is a positive relationship and the role of shadow teachers in inclusive schools to develop academic support and social support in children with special needs. Thus, the support and role of shadow teachers is very necessary for children with special needs.

The findings of the study conducted by Sabatin, [25] highlight the need for Shadow teachers who play an important role in providing additional support, throughout the school day, academically and psychologically, to students enrolled in Optimal learning (OL) programs who need this additional support. Special assistant teachers have the responsibility to support the ability of children with special needs in learning.

Based on the studies that have been discussed previously, there are several roles of special assistant teachers in inclusive schools, including in terms of program preparation. Based on research by Sowiyah & Perdana [26], it states that special assistant teachers need to prepare an Individual Learning Program (PPI) designed for one student, because the conditions make it impossible to follow a classical/Collective Learning Program.

This review had limitations among others; first, the articles were reviewed only in English and bahasa indonesia so other studies were not reviewed due to their limitations. Second, the scope of the article reviewed is still very limited, the scope of this study is only limited to research conducted in Asian countries, while the variety of Asian countries reviewed is still lacking and is needed for further research.. Thirdly, dissertations and theses are not included in the review, this can lead to publication bias in the results.

V. CONCLUSION

Based on the results of the literature review that researchers have done, it can be concluded that the role of special assistant teachers in inclusive schools is very necessary in assisting children with special needs. In addition, there is a need for collaboration and coordination with classroom teachers and other teachers and parents in assisting children with special needs. The role of special assistant teachers, among others, is able to design individual learning programs (PPI) and mentoring strategies for each child. This is one part that needs to be considered so that teachers can conduct assessments in each lesson. Thus, a special accompanying teacher can evaluate the entire process of the accompanied child. In addition, special assistant teachers also have a role to encourage interaction and communication between children with special needs and their classmates. From this point of view, the special accompanying teacher needs to understand and implement his tasks and responsibilities in an inclusive school.

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